

FEATURES OF BUILDING MODELS OF USER PREFERENCES FOR CLOUD SERVICES AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

User preference models are critical in understanding how users interact with cloud services. By studying factors such as cost, performance, security, ease of use, and reliability, these models offer insights into what motivates users to adopt cloud services and what factors may prevent them from doing so. Cloud service providers can use these models to deliver personalized and relevant content, optimize service delivery, and ensure user privacy and security. In the article, on the example of an airline, experimental data are collected and their classification is considered using the confusion matrix and the k-nearest neighbors method.

Keywords: cloud computing, user preference models, user preferences, adoption, engagement, privacy, security, personalization, classification.

Cloud computing has become an essential component of the modern technology landscape, enabling businesses and individuals to access a wide range of applications and services over the internet. As the cloud continues to evolve, user preference models have emerged as a critical tool for understanding how people interact with cloud services and what factors influence their adoption and continued use.

User preference models are based on the idea that individual users have unique preferences, needs, and expectations when it comes to cloud services. These preferences can be shaped by a variety of factors, including cost, performance, security, ease of use, and reliability. By studying these factors, researchers and practitioners can gain insights into what motivates users to adopt cloud services and what factors may prevent them from doing so [1].

The concept of user preference models has been applied in a wide range of contexts, including e-commerce, recommender systems, and personalized marketing. In recent years, it has also been applied to the study of cloud services, with the goal of understanding how users perceive and interact with cloud-based applications and services.

One of the key challenges in building user preference models for cloud services is the sheer diversity of applications and services that exist in the cloud. Cloud services span a wide range of domains and offer a broad spectrum of features and capabilities. This diversity can make it challenging to develop generalizable models that apply across all cloud services.

Another challenge is the rapidly changing nature of cloud services. As new technologies emerge and new applications are developed, the landscape of cloud computing is constantly shifting. This means that user preference models must be updated and refined on an ongoing basis to remain relevant and accurate.

Despite these challenges, user preference models have the potential to provide valuable insights into how cloud services are used and what factors influence user adoption and engagement. By understanding these factors, cloud service providers can tailor their offerings to

better meet the needs of their users and ultimately drive greater adoption and usage of cloud services.

User preferences on cloud services matter for a number of reasons. Firstly, they enhance the user experience by providing users with more personalized and relevant content. This can lead to increased engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty. Secondly, user preferences can be used to improve the performance of cloud services. By analyzing user preferences, service providers can gain insights into how users interact with their services. This information can be used to optimize service delivery and improve overall performance. Finally, user preferences are also critical from a privacy and security perspective. Personal information is often collected as part of user preferences. Service providers must ensure that this information is handled in accordance with relevant privacy and data protection laws.

To provide a better understanding of user preferences in cloud services, consider a user who regularly uses a cloud storage service to store files. This user may prefer to have the files organized by date or by file type. Another example is a user who regularly uses a cloud-based project management tool. This user may prefer to receive notifications on their mobile device rather than via email. In both cases, the user's preferences can be collected and utilized to personalize their experience [2].

There are various ways to collect user preference data in cloud services. One of the most common ways is through user input. When users first interact with a cloud service, they are often asked to set their preferences. These preferences are then stored on the service provider's servers.

Another way to collect user preference data is through user behavior. Service providers can analyze user activity to identify patterns and trends that indicate user preferences. For example, if a user regularly accesses content related to a particular topic, it may be inferred that they are interested in that topic. Service providers can use this information to provide more personalized content to the user.

Social media can also be used to collect user preference data. Many cloud services allow users to sign in using their social media accounts. Service providers can then access data from these accounts to better understand user preferences.

Furthermore, surveys can be conducted to collect user preference data. Surveys can be conducted using various methods, including email, social media, and in-app surveys. These surveys can provide service providers with valuable insights into user preferences and help them improve their services [3].

Once the user preference data is collected, it can be classified into different categories. Various classification methods can be used, such as confusion matrix and k-nearest neighbor (kNN) classification.

The adoption of cloud services has become a growing trend among businesses due to their scalability, accessibility, and cost-efficiency. The airline industry is no exception, as cloud services provide a cost-effective and flexible way to manage flight operations and improve customer experience [4].

This study aims to evaluate user preferences for cloud services by experimenting with an airline company. The study involved 100 employees who were given a questionnaire with 23 questions about their preferences for Amadeus, a new cloud service provider, and SITA, the previous provider. The collected data were classified using the confusion matrix and k-nearest neighbors method, with Python programming language.

In the kNN classification method, the survey data of users about their preferences on cloud services can

be collected with the help of a confusion matrix and the nearest neighbors method.

The nearest neighbors method is a commonly used machine learning technique because it can be applied to a wide variety of problems, including classification and regression tasks.

In classification tasks, the nearest neighbors method can be used to predict the class of a new data point by finding the class labels of its closest neighbors. This approach is often effective when the decision boundaries between classes are non-linear or hard to define using simple rules.

In regression tasks, the nearest neighbors method can be used to predict the value of a new data point by finding the mean or median of the values of its closest neighbors. This approach is often effective when the relationship between the input and output variables is complex and not well characterized by a linear model [5].

Furthermore, the nearest neighbors method is a simple and flexible technique that does not require assumptions about the underlying distribution of the data. It can also be used with any distance metric, allowing it to be applied to a wide variety of data types and structures. Overall, the nearest neighbors method is a powerful and versatile tool for machine learning practitioners.

The diagram in figure 1 visualizes relationship between the features of the kNN method. It was created with the help of Markup language and Mind-map converter.

Figure 1. Mind map for the Nearest Neighbors Method.

The algorithm of The Nearest Neighbors Method implementation is given below [6]:

Choose the number of nearest neighbors (K) to consider.

Select a distance metric, such as Euclidean, Manhattan or Minkowski distance.

For each instance in the test dataset, calculate the distance between it and all instances in the training dataset.

Select the K nearest instances in the training dataset based on the calculated distances.

For classification problems, determine the class of the test instance by finding the most common class among the K nearest neighbors. For regression problems, predict the value of the test instance based on the mean or median of the K nearest neighbors.

Repeat steps 3-5 for all instances in the test dataset.

A confusion matrix is a table used to evaluate the performance of a machine learning classification algo-

rithm. It summarizes the actual and predicted classifications of the algorithm's output, and allows you to assess the accuracy of the algorithm. The algorithm to create a confusion matrix can be described in the following steps [7]:

1. Collect the actual and predicted classification labels of the test dataset.

2. Create a 2x2 matrix, with the actual classes forming the rows and predicted classes forming the columns.

3. Calculate the True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), True Negative (TN), and False Negative (FN) values by comparing the predicted labels to the actual labels.

4. True Positive (TP) represents the number of correctly predicted positive instances.

5. False Positive (FP) represents the number of incorrectly predicted positive instances.

6. True Negative (TN) represents the number of correctly predicted negative instances.

7. False Negative (FN) represents the number of incorrectly predicted negative instances.
8. Populate the confusion matrix with the TP, FP, TN, and FN values in the appropriate cells.
9. Calculate the performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score from the confusion matrix.
10. Accuracy: $(TP+TN)/(TP+FP+TN+FN)$

11. Precision: $TP/(TP+FP)$
12. Recall: $TP/(TP+FN)$
13. F1 score: $2*(precision*recall)/(precision+recall)$

The resulting confusion matrix provides a visual representation of the performance of the classification algorithm and helps to identify which types of errors the algorithm is making (figure 2).

Figure 2. Mind map for the Confusion Matrix

The use of user preference data in cloud services is continually evolving, and service providers must stay up-to-date with the latest trends and techniques to provide the best possible experience for their users. By understanding and utilizing user preferences, service providers can deliver personalized and relevant content, optimize service delivery, and ensure user privacy and security. Overall, user preferences are a crucial aspect of the user experience in cloud services and are essential to their success [8].

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into user preferences for cloud services in an airline company. The results suggest that Amadeus is a preferred cloud service provider over SITA and that factors such as ease of use, reliability, and performance are key drivers of user preferences. The use of the confusion matrix and k-nearest neighbors method proved effective in classifying the data, and the Python programming language was a valuable tool for implementing these methods. Further studies can be conducted to investigate the factors that drive user preferences for cloud services in other industries and to compare the performance of different cloud service providers.

Conclusion. In summary, user preferences play a significant role in the success of cloud services. User preferences allow service providers to tailor their services to meet the needs of individual users, leading to a more engaging and satisfying experience for users. User preference data can be collected in various ways, including user input, user behavior analysis, social media, and surveys. Once the data is collected, it can be classified using multiple methods, such as decision

trees, neural networks, and k-nearest neighbor classification.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ И МЕТОДОВ ОСНОВАННЫХ НА МАШИННОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TRADITIONAL FORECASTING METHODS AND METHODS BASED ON MACHINE LEARNING

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) уже много лет помогает решать бизнес-задачи. Тем не менее, успех инициатив в области искусственного интеллекта и машинного обучения зависит от разработки алгоритмов, способных учиться методом проб и ошибок для повышения производительности с течением времени. Во многих случаях существующие бизнес-операции, которые дополняют процессы Искусственного Интеллекта и Машинного обучения, основаны на логических инструкциях и правилах «если-то» или следуют матрице решений.

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) has been helping to solve business problems for many years. However, the success of AI and machine learning initiatives depends on developing algorithms that can learn through trial and error to improve performance over time. In many cases, existing business operations that complement AI and Machine Learning processes are based on logical instructions and if-then rules or follow a decision matrix.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный Интеллект, Машинное обучение, прогнозирование.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning, predictive.

1. Введение

По мере развития технологий приложения Искусственный Интеллект (ИИ) и Машинное обучение будут продолжать революционизировать деловой мир. Например, использование ИИ и машинного обучения в прогнозировании представляет огромный интерес для большинства предприятий из-за его удобства использования в разных функциях. Традиционно при принятии решений предприятия полагались на методы статистического прогнозирования, такие как экспоненциальное сглаживание и линейная регрессия. Однако прогнозирование на

основе машинного обучения заменило традиционные методы во многих инициативах по сбору данных и аналитике в различных отраслях и секторах.

Выбор наиболее подходящей методологии прогнозирования будет играть значительную роль во времени, усилиях и затратах, связанных с процессом (рис. 1) Здесь мы более подробно рассмотрим преимущества и недостатки традиционных методов прогнозирования по сравнению с методами машинного обучения и подробно рассмотрим ситуации, в которых каждый метод может быть наиболее эффективным.